

Statistical Modeling of Historical Events as a Teaching Tool

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Abstract

We will discuss our work in introducing students to techniques of modeling and quantitative applications in their own area of study, specifically in areas outside of mathematics such as social sciences and humanities. This work is a component of a larger project funded by NSF titled “Math-Stat Modeling Across the Curriculum “. We will be focusing on projects which involve data from historical events, such as World War II and using technology and statistical methods to analyze, draw conclusions, and separate myth from facts. Projects require only knowledge of elementary statistics and mathematics. A common feature of these projects is the use of real data and commonly available technology to model historical events relevant to the specific disciplines.

Key Words: modeling, quantitative, applied, history, statistics

1. Introduction

In 2019, Texas Lutheran University was awarded a grant from The National Science Foundation, NSF-IUSE program (award # 1905246) for a project titled “Mathematical and Statistical Projects Across the Curriculum: Empowering Non-STEM Students to Appreciate and Use Quantitative Modeling” to be conducted during the period from October 2019 to September 2022. The project was intended to serve a national interest to improve attitudes, awareness, and use of quantitative modeling among students in the social sciences, applied sciences, arts, humanities, and other non-STEM disciplines. The main goals of the project were to increase students’ positive attitude, awareness, and appreciation of the relevance of mathematics and statistics through the application of quantitative modeling and the use of technology to solve problems related to topics of interest and to increase usage of modeling projects outside mathematics courses through project dissemination and the development of an online archive of peer-reviewed modeling projects.

Building a library of peer-reviewed modeling projects was an essential part of this project. In Summer of 2020 through 2022, the PI’s and collaborating faculty developed discipline-specific mathematical and statistical modeling projects which were used in classrooms and their impact on students’ attitude were measured through pre and post surveys. For decades the authors have been true believers in the power of technology, CAS, and online resources as investigative tools to help develop students understanding and appreciation of mathematics and statistics. This work gives us an opportunity to reach out across disciplinary boundaries and introduce non-STEM students, who in some cases are unaware of or fearful of quantitative methods, to the power of quantitative reasoning which can be beneficial in almost every field of study. We will begin our paper with rationale and methodology for our project which includes a brief description of the NSF grant that has been a major contributor to the success of our project. We will end the paper with introducing a sample of projects in modeling historical events.

2. Rationale and Methodology

In our academic careers we have seen students and others (particularly individuals with non-STEM majors or jobs) who claim they hate math or never understood the reasons behind taking math or statistics courses. Inability to conduct sound quantitative analysis of problems in business, political science, sociology, history, art, etc. is a major shortcoming for many college graduates, specifically non-STEM majors. At the same time, increasingly decisions of importance to us all are being made through quantitative analysis of data. Students often take math and statistics classes, but studies have shown that techniques learned in the math/statistics classroom may not transfer to other classrooms. An educated person must be aware of the importance of quantitative applications in their field. They need to learn to appreciate the relevance of quantitative applications and use of technology. To that end we designed our project “Mathematical and Statistical Modeling Across the Disciplines.” Among the goals of that project are 1) Through creating real life projects expose non-STEM students to some aspect of quantitative reasoning in a course or courses in their discipline, 2) Create an archive of modules that non-STEM faculty can incorporate into their class with a minimum of effort and planning on their part. Creating an archive of modeling projects was an essential part of this project. Faculty from various non-STEM fields joined us in creating short projects relevant to their discipline. The NSF grant allowed us to offer generous stipends to faculty during the summer session to compensate them for their time. Experienced faculty from math, computer science and physics were assigned as mentors to each participating non-STEM faculty to facilitate the development of quantitative modules that would be useful in their own classroom and interesting to others in other disciplines. Through this process we created numerous modules that were tested and are available for use in the classes of any faculty member who wishes to participate. During the fall and spring semesters, faculty assign these modules to their student with specific instructions. The goal is to teach students how to research a topic and then, using their faculty members’ instructions, which usually include the use of software, teams of students model the problem at hand and present the results. An important component of this process is use of technology that makes many formerly time-consuming and difficult tasks available to undergraduate students with minimal knowledge of math and statistics. Each project includes a student version and an instructor’s notes and are available to the public at: www.tlumathcsis.org. Instructor’s notes include information for the teaching faculty and will also be available to faculty outside TLU. We also invite faculty from TLU and other institutions to submit additional modeling projects for peer review and inclusion on the website. Participating faculty conducted a pre and post survey with their students. The survey was designed to measure the following factors: mathematical/statistical disposition, comfortableness using math/statistics applications and their perception of the value of quantified data. Analysis of the survey data disclosed modest gains. We note that in many cases negative attitudes toward quantitative work had been built over many years and clearly it will take many years to reverse the trend. Still, a small gain is a step in the correct direction. Various other bits of data came from the survey, for example that men made larger gains than women.

By original design the post-survey was given toward the end of the semester. In an effort to get more immediate feedback from students we created three “reflection questions” that were asked upon completion of the module. The questions were about change in attitudes and challenges and required narrative responses. The responses gave us another metric to measure the change in attitude due to use of modules and overall indicated that students they were getting a lot out of the modules and that there was an appreciation for quantitative modeling related to their discipline.

3. Examples of Modules

To demonstrate the type and degree of difficulty of modules, we will introduce a few examples, specifically projects related to modeling of historical events. Please note that our goal here is not

original research. We aim to introduce non-STEM students (and their faculty) to the power of quantitative modeling in investigations of historical events.

3.1 German Tank Problem

For obvious reasons it was of interest to the allied forces to know how many tanks German industry was able to produce. Equally obvious was that production was a closely guarded secret. However, using serial numbers from transmissions of captured and/or destroyed German tanks and a clever bit of statistics the British were able to closely estimate the production. The technique, which can be applied to many other historical and current estimation problems, is to let the number of captured tanks be represented by the letter K , and the maximum serial number we have seen be represented by the letter M , then we can estimate the maximum number of tanks with the equation:

$$\text{Max production} \approx M + \frac{M}{K} - 1$$

which can be shown to be the uniformly minimum unbiased estimator of the max production. But of course, in a, say, history class, one can explain the method and the useful results obtained without excessive use of higher-level statistical concepts.

3.2 Did Mark Twain write that?

In 1861 a series of humorous letters from Quintus Curtius Snodgrass were published in the New Orleans Daily Crescent. These letters chronicled the participation of the author in a local southern militia. In the years since 1861 there has been speculation that Quintus Curtius Snodgrass was a nom de plume of Samuel Clemens (Mark Twain). And why would this matter? In later years Samuel Clemens became a close friend and advisor of Ulysses S. Grant. From a Confederate sympathizer and participant to a prominent backer of the most important Union general and former U.S. President would be quite a journey. Is Samuel Clemens really Quintus Curtius Snodgrass? To investigate the question, we used “Stylometry.” Stylometry is a procedure that uses two or more lengthy samples of the supposed author’s writing. In this case our samples were the Snodgrass letters and uncontested stories written by Clemens. Using technology (R and a stylometry package) we removed from both samples: numbers, punctuation, “stop words” such as and, or, etc. Next, we count word frequency in each sample and perform “cluster analysis” (or other) measures of similarity on the samples. Did Mark Twain write the Quintus Curtius Snodgrass letters? Most likely Mark Twain is not the author of these letters.

3.3 London Bombing

From June through October 1944, Germany sent 9,521 copies of “vengeance weapon one” toward London. These weapons were referred to as V1-Bombs, Flying Bombs, Buzz Bombs, Doodle Bugs, etc. They were equipped with 850 kg of Amatol and were very destructive weapons. Due to range limitations most of these bombs fell on London and points South. Of huge concern was the accuracy of these weapons. If they were accurately targeting points, say ammunition depots, it would make sense to move the depots. However, if the strikes were random, it would be a wasted effort moving suspected targets about in the vulnerable zone. Meticulous records of hits were maintained and when plotted on maps of the area people believed they were not seeing random hits but could detect patterns. But of course, people would see patterns. Our eyes and brains are evolved to see patterns, whether the patterns are there or not. What was needed was a statistical test to decide the issue.

In 1944 R. D. Clark was a young actuary assigned to war duty in London. It was his idea that one could use statistics to decide the likelihood that V1 strikes on South England were random or targeted. Clark sectioned off on the British Ordnance map which recorded the V1 strikes a 144 sq km rectangle. Noting that strikes within the large rectangle were approximately uniform he further divided the large rectangle into 576 small squares, $\frac{1}{2}$ km on a side. Next, he counted the strikes in each of his 576 small squares and constructed a frequency distribution of number of squares with no hits, number with exactly one hit, number with two hits, and so forth up to number with five or more hits. Clark knew that by virtue of his work to this point, if the bomb strikes were in fact

random, the frequency distribution he had just created should have a probability mass function that was Poisson with parameter $\lambda = 537/576 = .9323$ (Actual number of hits in his large rectangle divided by number of small squares in his subdivision of the large rectangle.) Applying a Chi Squared Goodness of Fit Test, the p-value for the Chi Squared test was found by Clark to be 0.88 which is strong evidence that the observations fit a Poisson Distribution which in turn confirms the assumption of a uniform initial distribution of V1 bombs.

In 2021 our student built a computer simulation that sent 537 virtual bombs to London, in particular the virtual bomb strikes were within a 144 square km portion of England including London and an area South. The random location of the strikes was recorded, the 144 sq km rectangle was subdivided into 576 sub-squares, each $\frac{1}{4}$ sq km in area, and following Clarke's procedure a frequency distribution of number of hits in each grid area was constructed. Our Chi Squared test indicated, as did Clark's, that the strikes were random.

In a second round of experimentation four targets were selected and varying numbers of bombs were sent to these targets (total 268). The accuracy of the simulated guidance systems was adjustable and included randomly assigned errors. Other bombs (269) were sent to London without targeting.

This project is particularly nice because of the many and varied topics, in addition to statistical analysis, that it introduces. For example: exploration of the geographical relation between the launch sites in France and the South of England, the engineering that went into both the design of the V1 missile and the counter measures designed by the Allies, economic analysis of the use of what today we call cruise missiles vs maned strikes, to name but a few.

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